

Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from a shipwreck found at Peenemündung, Germany – Ostsee VII, Fpl 105.

by

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Five samples from a shipwreck found at Peenemündung, Germany, were submitted for dendrochronological analysis, to determine their date and provenance. Four samples were previously examined and the wreck was dated to c. AD 1419-20 (Daly 2018). The additional samples are analysed to further examine the provenance of the timbers used to build this ship. The results of this analysis are described in this report.

Peenemündung, Germany – Fpl 105

Combining the two analyses, a total of nine samples are now examined from the ship. The samples come from the keel, from two frames, from five planks and from a repair. All the samples analysed from the ship are of *Quercus sp.*, oak. Eight samples are dated.

Fig. 1. Peenemündung, Ostsee VII, Fpl 105. The chronological position of the dated samples.

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The keel

The sample from the keel contains 68 tree-rings including 16 sapwood rings. The tree for the keel is relatively fast-grown, with an average ring width of 2.2 mm. The sample could not be dated.

The frames

The sample from frame 302 (Z2230029) contains 154 tree-rings. This sample has only heartwood preserved. This sample is dated. The tree-ring curve covers the period AD 1233-1386. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree used to make this frame is estimated to be after AD 1397. The sample from frame 303 (Z223007a) contains 141 tree-rings that could be measured, and there are an additional c. 20 heartwood rings outermost, that were too narrow to allow reliable measurement. The tree that this sample comes from was felled after AD 1378. If the two trees for the frames were felled at the same time, this felling took place after AD 1397 (marked with purple in fig. 1).

				Z2230029	Z223007a	Z223003a	Z223006a	Z223008a	Z2230099	Z223004a	Z223005a
Ave Z223 M002	frame	302	Z2230029	*	3.69	-	-	-	-	-	-
	frame	303	Z223007a	3.69	*	-	-	-	-	-	-
Average Z223M001	plank	316	Z223003a	-	-	*	4.27	5.98	-	3.92	-
	plank	323	Z223006a	-	-	4.27	*	7.27	4.99	-	-
	plank	313	Z223008a	-	-	5.98	7.27	*	4.03	-	-
	plank	312	Z2230099	-	-	-	4.99	4.03	*	-	-
	plank	315	Z223004a	-	-	3.92	-	-	-	*	-
	repair	314	Z223005a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	*

Table 1. Peenemündung, Ostsee VII, Fpl 105. Correlation between each dated sample and each other. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

The planks

All five planks are dated. Two of the plank samples have sapwood preserved.

Plank 316 (p3) has five sapwood rings. The tree used for this plank was felled in the period c. AD 1415-29. Plank 315 (p4) has 24 sapwood rings preserved.

Allowing for missing sapwood the felling date for this tree can be placed at c. AD 1419-20. The three other plank samples are from trees felled after AD 1392, after AD 1399 and after AD 1403 respectively.

If we assume that the trees for the planks were felled in the same event, this felling took place around 1419-20 (marked with green in fig. 1).

If the planks and frames are from trees felled around the same time, then we might estimate that the ship was built around AD 1420.

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Repair

A repair piece (314 Z223005a) has only heartwood preserved. It is from a tree felled after AD 1394 (marked with blue in fig. 1). Unfortunately, it does not give us any indication of when the repair was carried out.

Provenance

The correlation between the tree-ring curves from the dated samples from the ship with each other is shown in table 1. Four planks form a group and an average of these is made (Z223M001) of 286 years in length. The two frames can also be assigned a group and these two are averaged to a mean curve of 178 years (Z223M002).

Filename	-	-	Planks Z223M001	
-	start	dates	AD1126	
-	dates	end	AD1411	
<i>Master and site chronologies</i>				
0M040005	AD1257	AD1615	10.79	Baltic 2 40 timbers (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
P823001m	AD1236	AD1447	7.79	Poland Ruziec (Wazny pers comm)
PM670108	AD725	AD1985	7.24	PL Gdansk (Wazny pers comm)
0M040004	AD1156	AD1597	6.85	Baltic 1 64 timbers (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
S00940M01	AD1099	AD1354	6.13	Gotland altarpiece Endre church 9 timbers (Bartholin et al 1999b)
PM000003	AD1102	AD1431	6.02	Gdansk Pomerania (Wazny pers comm)
PP118M01	AD1112	AD1399	5.97	PL Gdansk various 31 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
P671001m	AD980	AD1347	5.97	Poland Elblag (Wazny pers comm)
PP106M01	AD1110	AD1399	5.85	PL Gdansk Parc.6 14 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
P720404M	AD1192	AD1452	5.84	PL Pultusk (Wazny pers comm)
<i>Chronologies from ships or barrels</i>				
CLS2000	AD1110	AD1393	12.16	Hull Chapel Lane Yorkshire 11 boat planks (Tyers pers comm)
Z076m001	AD1097	AD1393	12.11	Skjernøysund 3 strong group 14 timbers (Daly 2011)
HMC_T165	AD1078	AD1369	11.70	Hull boards from 37 coffins Yorkshire (Tyers pers comm)
02071M01	AD1126	AD1414	8.73	Dokøen Vrag 2 (Eriksen 2001)
2129M001	AD1125	AD1399	8.42	Copenhagen Niels Hemmingsensgade barrel 3 timbers (Daly 2000)
GAS_SHIP	AD1052	AD1370	8.31	London Southwark 10 timbers (Tyers pers comm)
se617M01	AD1100	AD1396	7.91	New Baxtergate Grims 5 timbers (Sheffield Uni revised Daly 2007)
Z005M003	AD1063	AD1373	7.65	Bølevraget planks 4 timbers (Daly & Nymoen 2008)
os160_t7	AD1138	AD1382	7.56	York Vicars Choral Large Table 7 boards (Tyers pers comm)
P0011009	AD1103	AD1403	6.95	Copper Ship wainscots (Wazny pers comm)
Z034m001	AD1188	AD1371	6.90	Bovet Læsø vrag 2 timbers (Daly unpubl 2009)
00751M03	AD1221	AD1456	6.77	Vejdyb ship 4 trees (Daly 1997)
D0132M02 staves	AD1096	AD1336	6.10	Thomas B Thriges staves 7 timbers (Daly 2016)
se629m01	AD1118	AD1386	5.82	York Minster Zouche 4 timbers (Sheffield Uni revised Daly 2007)
StCrux27	AD1144	AD1388	5.77	York St Crux Church decorative bosses (Tyers pers comm)

Table 2. Peenemündung, Ostsee VII, Fpl 105. Result of the correlation between the average for four planks (Z223M001) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

The correlation between the tree-ring average from the planks is shown in table 2. It is achieving highest correlation with a chronology called Baltic 2 and with chronologies from objects and structures from the Southern Baltic region. Plank 315 is also dating with Southern Baltic datasets, particularly with chronologies from Gdansk (table 3). All the planks seem to be made from trees of Southern Baltic origin, but plank 315 might have grown in a different part of the region to the other four.

Filenames	-	-	plank 315 p4 Z223004a	
-	start	Dates	AD 1200	
-	dates	End	AD 1419	
<i>Master and site chronologies</i>				
PM670108	AD 725	AD 1985	5.93	PL Gdansk (Wazny pers comm)
PP118M01	AD 1112	AD 1399	5.60	PL Gdansk various 31 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP106M01	AD 1110	AD 1399	5.44	PL Gdansk Parc.6 14 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
0686003S	AD 1140	AD 1390	5.37	PL Przewmark (Wazny pers comm)
PP107M01	AD 1221	AD 1399	5.37	PL Gdansk Stagiewna 2 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
P822001m	AD 1185	AD 1320	4.98	Poland Malbork (Wazny pers comm)
PP127M01	AD 1341	AD 1501	4.97	PL Kwidzyn 5 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP126M01	AD 1017	AD 1393	4.96	PL Elblag 137 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
<i>Chronologies from ships or barrels</i>				
0204M001	AD 1187	AD 1414	5.89	Tårnby Amager ship timbers 2 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Z103M003	AD 1234	AD 1495	5.07	Slagen altertavle Norge 14 timbers (Daly 2013)
w439M01	AD 1157	AD 1299	5.00	Horsens barrel 3 timbers (Sønderby pers comm Daly 2007)
B0352M01	AD 1306	AD 1451	4.64	Roskilde Stændertorvet 3 dele af tøndebund (Daly 2015)
0244M003	AD 1219	AD 1406	4.54	Mellelgade 21 Nibe 6 timbers (Eriksen pers comm 2011)
Z076m003 all	AD 1097	AD 1393	4.36	Skjernøysund 3 all 19 timbers (Daly 2011)
2129M001	AD 1125	AD 1399	4.02	Niels Hemmingsensgade tønne 3 timbers (Daly 2000)

Table 3. Peenemündung, Ostsee VII, Fpl 105. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve for plank 315 (Z223004a) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Filenames	-	-	Frames Z223M002	
-	start	dates	AD1209	
-	dates	End	AD1386	
<i>Master and site chronologies</i>				
2x900001	AD830	AD1997	7.80	Sjælland Denmark 227 timbers (Nationalmuseet)
LUNQSP01	AD621	AD1769	7.80	Lund oak (Bartholin pers comm)
SM000001	AD651	AD1496	6.49	Sydvest Skåne (Lund University)
H11JPM02	AD1135	AD1301	6.45	HL Fischstr. 14 6 timbers Swedish? (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
PP111M01	AD1136	AD1399	6.39	PL Gdansk St Nikolaus 11 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
ZEALAND0	AD452	AD1770	6.35	Sjælland Denmark 249 timbers (Daly unpubl)
00000059	AD1101	AD1350	5.88	Svendborg Denmark (Bartholin pers comm)
0680001S	AD1121	AD1398	5.83	Gdansk St Nikolaus (Wazny pers comm)
P676001m	AD1084	AD1393	5.50	Poland Kolobrzeg (Wazny pers comm)
OHEL0001	AD1197	AD1490	5.37	Helsingborg (Eggertsson pers comm)
<i>Chronologies from ships and barrels</i>				
0056M001	AD1174	AD1335	6.29	Aberdeen barrel (Crone pers comm)
0045M002	AD1109	AD1370	6.19	Vejby skib 18 trees (Bonde & Jensen 1995)
0059m001	AD1264	AD1434	6.07	Vedby Hage ship (Daly & Eriksen 1996)
SM000012	AD1125	AD1720	5.32	Sverige Vest (Bråthen 1982)
4M000001	AD1058	AD1350	5.23	Danmark Svendborg (Nationalmuseet)
SM100003	AD1135	AD1711	5.15	Ystad area (Lund University)
PM000003	AD1102	AD1431	5.12	Gdansk Pomerania (Wazny pers comm)
PP109M01	AD1207	AD1333	5.11	PL Gdansk Spichrz 6 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
S0090M001	AD1054	AD1269	5.03	Gotland Ukendt kirke Retable Fornsalen (Bartholin et al 1999a)
DM100003	AD436	AD1968	5.02	Schleswig-Holstein (Hamburg Uni)
SM600002	AD859	AD1371	5.02	Småland-Öland (Lund University)

Table 4. Peenemündung, Ostsee VII, Fpl 105. Result of the correlation between the average for two frames (Z223M002) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Filenames	-	-	Repair 314 Z223005a	
-	start	dates	AD1245	
-	dates	end	AD1384	
<i>Master and site chronologies</i>				
PP117M01	AD1173	AD1394	6.51	PL Gdansk Lub.Okret 9 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP106M01	AD1110	AD1399	5.36	PL Gdansk Parc.6 14 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
P734002M	AD1247	AD1427	5.27	PL Bransk (Wazny pers comm)
OM040004	AD1156	AD1597	4.63	Baltic 1 64 timbers (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
PP118M01	AD1112	AD1399	4.62	PL Gdansk various 31 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
P815001M	AD1262	AD1503	4.61	PL Bielsk Podl. (Wazny pers comm)
<i>Chronologies from ships or barrels</i>				
StCruz27	AD1144	AD1388	7.92	York St Cruz Church decorative bosses (Tyers pers comm)
se629m01	AD1118	AD1386	7.61	York Minster Zouche 4 timbers (Sheffield Uni revised Daly 2007)
GAPCX7	AD1283	AD1450	7.24	Guthrie Aisle panels 7 timbers (Crone pers comm)
2129M001	AD1125	AD1399	6.44	Copenhagen Niels Hemmingsensgade barrel 3 timbers (Daly 2000)
os160_t7	AD1138	AD1382	6.14	York Vicars Choral Large Table 7 boards (Tyers pers comm)
GAS_SHIP	AD1052	AD1370	5.20	London Southwark 10 timbers (Tyers pers comm)
P0011009	AD1103	AD1403	5.19	Copper Ship wainscots (Wazny pers comm)
HMC_T165	AD1078	AD1369	4.72	Hull boards from 37 coffins Yorkshire (Tyers pers comm)
Z076m001	AD1097	AD1393	4.68	Skjernøysund 3 strong group 14 timbers (Daly 2011)
00751M03	AD1221	AD1456	4.63	Vejdyb ship 4 trees (Daly 1997)
02071M01	AD1126	AD1414	4.62	Dokøen Vrag 2 (Eriksen 2001)
CLS2000	AD1110	AD1393	4.61	Hull Chapel Lane Yorkshire 11 boat planks (Tyers pers comm)
se617M01	AD1100	AD1396	4.59	New Baxtergate Grims 5 timbers (Sheffield Uni revised Daly 2007)

Table 5. Peenemündung, Ostsee VII, Fpl 105. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve for the repair (314 Z223005a) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

As can be seen in table 4, the tree-ring average from the two frames is achieving high correlation with Southern Scandinavian datasets but high values also appear with chronologies from the southern Baltic. The t -values achieved are however not allowing a more specific identification of the provenance of the tree used for the frames.

The correlation between the tree-ring curve from the repair piece and diverse Northern European tree-ring datasets is shown in table 5.

This piece is achieving highest correlation with Southern Baltic datasets.

Methodology

Measuring and analysis of the material is carried out using the program "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and for the calculation of the t -value (" t -test") "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is used. To estimate the felling dates of the oak trees used for the frames a sapwood average of c. 10-25 sapwood rings is used. Several calculations of the average sapwood in oaks in different regions in Northern Europe have been published, and as the provenance of the oak for the frame points towards Southern Scandinavia, I have here chosen to use a combination of the estimate for Northern Germany (ca. 20 sapwood years (-5+10) (Hollstein 1980)) and for Northern Poland (15 years (-6 +9) (Wazny 1990)). To estimate the felling dates of the trees used for the planks, the sapwood average for Northern Poland (15 years (-6 +9) (Wazny 1990)) is applied. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are consulted.

Literature

- Baillie, M.G.L. and Pilcher, J.R., 1973. A simple crossdating program for tree-ring research. *Tree-Ring Bulletin* 33, 7-14.
- Bartholin, T., Bonde, N. & Daly, A., 1999a. Dendrokronologisk undersøgelse af altertavle fra "ukendt" kirke, Gotland. *Nationalmuseets Naturvidenskabelige Undersøgelser rapport* 1999:34, Copenhagen.
- Bartholin, T., Bonde, N. & Daly, A. 1999b. Dendrokronologisk undersøgelse af altertavle fra Endre kirke, Gotland. *Nationalmuseets Naturvidenskabelige Undersøgelser rapport* 1999:38, Copenhagen.
- Bonde, N. and Jensen, J.S., 1995. The dating of a Hanseatic cog-ship in Denmark. What coins and tree rings can reveal in maritime archaeology. in Olsen, O., J.S. Madsen and F. Rieck (eds.), *Shipshape. Essays for Ole-Crumlin-Pedersen. On the occasion of his 60th anniversary February 24th 1995*, Roskilde, 103-121.
- Bråthen, A. 1982. Dendrokronologisk serie från västra Sverige 813-1975. *Rapport Riksantikvarieämbetet och Statens historiska museer* 1982:1. Stockholm.
- Daly, A., 1997. Dendrokronologisk undersøgelse af skibsvrag fra Vejdyb udfor Hals, Aalborg Amt. *Nationalmuseets Naturvidenskabelige Undersøgelser rapport* 1997:12, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A., 2000. Dendrokronologisk undersøgelse af tømme fra Niels Hemmingsensgade, København, *Nationalmuseets Naturvidenskabelige Undersøgelser, report* 14, 2000, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A., 2007. *Timber, Trade and Tree-rings. A dendrochronological analysis of structural oak timber in Northern Europe, c. AD 1000 to c. AD 1650*. Ph.D. thesis submitted February 2007, University of Southern Denmark.
- Daly, A., 2011. Dendrochronological analysis of oak from a shipwreck, Skjernøysund 3, Mandal, Norway. *Chronology, Culture and Archaeology report* 2, University College Dublin, September 2011.
- Daly, A., 2013. Dendrochronological analysis of altarpiece from Slagen church, Norway, C2124. *CATS dendro report* 2, Copenhagen
- Daly, A., 2015. Dendrokronologiske undersøgelse af tømme fra Stændertorvet, Roskilde, ROM 3224. *Dendro.dk rapport* 2015:34, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A., 2016. Dateringsundersøgelse af tømme fra Thomas B Thriges gade, Odense: *Dendro.dk rapport* 2016:22, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A., 2018. Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from a shipwreck found at Peenemündung, Germany – Fpl 105. *Dendro.dk report* 2018:23, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A. & Eriksen, O.H., 1996. Dendrokronologisk undersøgelse af tømme fra skibsvrag fra Vedby Hage, Storstrøms Amt. *Nationalmuseets Naturvidenskabelige Undersøgelser rapport nr. 13*, 1996. Copenhagen.
- Daly A. & Nymoene P., 2008. The Bøle Ship, Skien, Norway – Research history, dendrochronology and provenance, *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology* 37.1, p. 153–170.
- Eriksen, O.H., 2001. Dendrokronologisk undersøgelse af tømme fra skibsvrag fundet på Dokøen, København. *Nationalmuseets Naturvidenskabelige Undersøgelser rapport* 2001:23, Copenhagen.
- Hillam, J. and Tyers, I., 1995. Reliability and repeatability in dendrochronological analysis: tests using the Fletcher archive of panel-painting data. *Archaeometry* 37, p. 395-405.

Hollstein, E. 1980. *Mitteleuropäische Eichenchronologie*. Trierer Grabungen und Forschungen 11. Mainz am Rhein.

Tyers, I.G., 1997. Dendro for Windows Program Guide, *ARCUS Report 340*, Sheffield.

Wazny, T., 1990. *Aufbau und Anwendung der Dendrochronologie für Eichenholz in Polen*. PhD Thesis. Universität Hamburg, pp. 213.

Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Fpl 105 Ship											
Z223001a	Peenemündung Ostsee VII Fpl 105 keel 301 p1 QUSP	68			V	16	N	O	N	2,20	undated
Z2230029	Peenemündung Ostsee VII Fpl 105 frame 302 p2 QUSP	154	AD 1233	AD 1386	C	0	N	S	H1	0,55	after AD 1397
Z223003a	Peenemündung Ostsee VII Fpl 105 plank 316 p3 QUSP	159	AD 1253	AD 1411	G	5	N	R	S1	1,82	AD 1415-29
Z223004a	Peenemündung Ostsee VII Fpl 105 plank 315 p4 QUSP	220	AD 1200	AD 1419	G	24	N	R	N	1,20	AD 1419-20
Z223005a	Peenemündung Ostsee VII Fpl 105 repair x8 314 SN 35417 QUSP	140	AD1245	AD1384	G	0	N	R	H1	0,90	after AD1394
Z223006a	Peenemündung Ostsee VII Fpl 105 plank x6 323 SN 35415 QUSP	216	AD1174	AD1389	G	0	N	R	H1	0,95	after AD1399
Z223007a	Peenemündung Ostsee VII Fpl 105 frame x7 303 SN 35413 QUSP	141	AD1209	AD1349	C	0	N	O	H20	0,63	after AD1378
Z223008a	Peenemündung Ostsee VII Fpl 105 plank x3 313 SN 35416 QUSP	159	AD1235	AD1393	G	0	N	R	H1	1,26	after AD1403
Z2230099	Peenemündung Ostsee VII Fpl 105 plank x5 312 SN 35414 QUSP	257	AD1126	AD1382	G	0	N	R	H1	0,83	after AD1392
Averages											
Z223M001	Peenemündung Ostsee VII Fpl 105 planks 4 timbers QUSP	286	AD1126	AD1411						1,08	
Z223M002	Peenemündung Ostsee VII Fpl 105 frames 2 timbers QUSP	178	AD1209	AD1386						0,65	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak. PISY = <i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix sp.</i> , spruce/larch											
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